

Performance-Accuracy Tradeoff in the Design of Hyperspectral Image Classification in FPGA

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Abstract—Hyperspectral remote sensing applications have been greatly increased in the last decades and are expected to continue growing in number in the near future. In time-critical scenarios, such as target detection for military purposes, monitoring of chemical contamination, or wildfire tracking, it is important to accelerate hyperspectral data analysis techniques. In order to avoid high data volume transmission bottlenecks and the associated delays, onboard processing is highly desirable. The recent deep learning models have shown very good results on image classification and therefore have been applied also in hyperspectral image classification. However, running these algorithms in low-power on-board devices is a challenging task since they require high computing power and memory. Architectural optimizations and performance accuracy tradeoffs must be established to find a computing solution that guarantees the real-time analysis of hyperspectral images. This paper analyzes the performance accuracy tradeoff of a deep learning model for hyperspectral image analysis and classification. Changing the characteristics of the model and quantizing its parameters leads to different ratios between performance and accuracy when implemented in FPGA. The results show that the computational solution can be considerably improved with negligible accuracy reduction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) collects valuable information from monitoring the surface of the Earth [1]. This information is used in many remote sensing application, including environmental management [2], agriculture [3] and surveillance [4]. In time-critical scenarios, such as target detection for military purposes, monitoring of chemical contamination, or wildfire tracking, it is important to accelerate hyperspectral data analysis techniques.

Hyperspectral image classification is currently a very active area of research. Latest generation hyperspectral imaging instruments have very high spatial, spectral, and temporal resolution, which potentially enables more powerful capabilities in sensed information processing and interpretation. However, the vast amount of data generated by these systems makes data processing and analysis tasks computationally very heavy [5].

It is highly desirable that hyperspectral information processing is performed onboard when real-time data analysis is necessary. However, to process data onboard, it is desirable that the hardware integrated components have low-weight and

low-power which are essential to reduce the mission payload in satellites, aircrafts or unnamed aerial vehicles. Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) and low-power embedded Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) platforms are a good choice for developing onboard hyperspectral signal processing tasks such as compression, image classification and target detection [6]. However, only few works introduce similar approaches for onboard missions [7], [8].

Recently, deep learning has attracted much attention and has been applied to many domains such as object detection, image classification and unmixing [9], [10]. In particular, the convolutional neural network (CNN) [10], [11] is one of the most popular network owing to its capability to automatically discover relevant contextual features. However, the task is more challenging when applied to hyperspectral images with a third spectral dimension and limited training labeled data. Several researchers have tried to address this problem by proposing adequate solutions to reduce the necessary amount of data required in the training phase. A residual network with scattering transform features (ARNST) [12] and a generative adversarial networks (GAN) [13] based semi-supervised method are two models trained for hyperspectral classifications with relatively limited data.

A few hardware implementations of simple deep learning architectures had been introduced for the classification of hyperspectral images. A model with two convolutional layers was implemented in an NVIDIA Jetson Tegra TX2 device, offering a good compromise in term of performance, cost, and energy consumption [14]. The model was tested with two public datasets: Indian Pines and University of Pavia dataset. However, some implementation based on FPGA [15] had focused on maximizing data reuse and minimizing external memory bandwidth rather than the implemented architecture. The accelerator proposed in [15] implemented on a Xilinx Zynq 706 FPGA board, is 70 time faster than an Intel 8-coreXeon CPU and 3 time faster than an NVIDIA GeForce 1080 GPU. In fact, the implemented architecture is composed with 5 convolutional layers, and draws very encouraging results on relatively small public datasets (namely Indian Pines and others). Hence, within larger datasets the problem become more challenging since more sophisticated architectures are requested to attend high classification results. Another work [16] proposes a model which takes in consideration two aspects:

machine balance and code balance. In fact, authors provide a model able to distinguish between resources provided by FPGA hardware and resources requested by the application. The CNN suggested implementation uses a 2D connection scheme among the number of processing elements to allow efficient data sharing without memory replication. In addition to a 2D dispatcher to support the proposed interconnection and a Work Item scheduling technique to further optimize memory usage. Moreover, to reduce the external memory bandwidth, a shared buffer technique was adopted.

None of these works consider hardware oriented optimization of the model to improve the performance of the system. In this paper, we analyze the tradeoff between performance and accuracy of the deep learning model for spectral-spatial hyperspectral image classification proposed in [17] targeting the FPGA technology. The study considers the following aspects:

- 1) Model quantization - parameters of the model are converted to fixed-point where the number of quantization bits varies from 1 to 8;
- 2) Model configuration - the model includes a set of configurable parameters that change the complexity and the accuracy of the network. The main configuration parameter - patch size - will be considered in the design space exploration. The range of values depends on the dataset;
- 3) Datasets - Two well-known hyperspectral data sets have been considered in this work: Indian Pines (IP) and University of Pavia (UP).

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the deep learning model for hyperspectral classification. Section 3 describes the optimization process of the model. Section 4 details the performance accuracy tradeoff. Section 5 concludes the paper.

II. MODEL FOR HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGE CLASSIFICATION

The hyperspectral image is a data cube with dimensions $N \times W \times H$, where W (width) and H (Height) are spatial dimensions and N is a spectral dimension representing the number of bands (see Figure 1).

The hyperspectral image classification problem consists in finding the class of each pixel from a pre-determined set of classes. Each pixel is classified according to its spectral signature and the spatial neighborhoods. To classify the hyperspectral pixels, the deep learning model proposed in [17] was considered. The deep learning model receives a cube of size $N \times D \times D$ and determines the class of the pixel at the center of the cube. The classification can be applied to all pixels of the image so that the full image is classified at the pixel level.

The model is based on the ResNet model [18] that allows deep models with many layers to be trained without suffering from the vanishing gradient problem. The model has 28 convolutional layers, with batch normalization, three downsampling layers and nine ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) layers (see Figure 2).

Fig. 1. Hyperspectral image to classify

The first column of layers represented in Figure 2 keeps the size of the spatial map with a stride equal to 1. In the second and third columns of layers, two mechanisms are used to downsample the input data: convolutions with stride of two and downsample layers. The last downsampling layer applies average pooling over the input data to reduce data variance and extract low-level features from the spatial neighborhood. Instead of following the traditional residual units, the pyramidal ResNet approach was adopted to calculate the depth at the end of each set of the convolutional layers. The output feature map of the last sequence of layers is downsampled one last time with average pooling and reshaped as a vector before entering a fully connected layer to run the classification layer.

III. OPTIMIZATION OF THE COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY OF THE MODEL

The execution of the model can be accelerated by approximating the computation at the cost of minimal accuracy drop. One of the most common strategies is reducing the precision of operations. During training, the data is typically in single-precision floating-point format. For inference in FPGAs, the feature maps and kernels data are usually converted to fixed-point format with less precision, typically 8 bits, reducing the storage requirements, hardware utilization and power consumption [19].

Quantization is done by reducing the operand bit size. This restricts the operand resolution, affecting the resolution of the computation result. Furthermore, representing the operands in fixed-point instead of floating-point translates into another reduction in terms of required resources for computation.

Fig. 2. Model for hyperspectral image classification

The simplest quantization method consists of setting all weights and inputs to the same format across all layers of the network. This is referred to as static fixed-point (SFP). However, the intermediate values still need to be bit-wider to prevent further accuracy loss.

In deep networks, there is a significant variety of data ranges across the layers. The inputs tend to have larger values at later layers, while the weights for the same layers are smaller in comparison. The wide range of values makes the SFP approach not viable since the bit-width needs to expand to accommodate all values.

This problem is addressed by Dynamic Fixed-Point (DFP), which consists of the attribution of different scaling factors to the inputs, weights and outputs of each layer.

Table I presents an accuracy comparison between floating-point and DFP implementations for two known neural networks. The fixed-point precision representation leads to an accuracy loss of less than 1%.

Quantization was applied to the CNN of the model considered in this paper. Quantizations of both weight and activations were considered with bitwidth sizes from 1 to 8.

Batch-normalization folding is another important opti-

TABLE I. ACCURACY COMPARISON WITH THE IMAGENET DATASET, ADAPTED FROM [20].

Model Accuracy Comparison	Single Float Precision		Fixed-Point Precision	
	Top-1	Top-5	Top-1	Top-5
AlexNet [21]	56.78%	79.72%	55.64%	79.32%
NIN [22]	56.14%	79.32%	55.74%	78.96%

mization method that folds the parameters of the batch-normalization layer into the preceding convolutional layer. This reduces the number of parameters and operations of the model. The method updates the pre-trained floating-point weights w and biases b to w' and b' according to Eq. 1 before applying quantization.

$$w' = \frac{\gamma \times w}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}} \quad b' = b - \frac{\mu \times \gamma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon}} \quad (1)$$

where the mean, μ , and the variance, σ^2 , are statistics collected from training. The scale factor, γ , are parameters learned during training. ϵ is a small constant that avoids dividing by zero.

Batch-normalization folding was also considered during the quantization aware training of the hyperspectral model.

TABLE II. ACCURACY OF THE HYPERSPECTRAL MODEL WITH DIFFERENT QUANTIZATIONS AND DIFFERENT PATCH SIZES FOR THE IP DATASET

Dataset: IP						
	Patch size (D)					
	7	9	11	15	19	21
8×8	98.74	99.41	99.53	99.59	99.64	99.73
4×4	98.55	99.10	99.33	99.52	99.57	99.61
2×2	91.72	94.67	96.15	98.31	98.54	98.66
1×1	84.79	93.98	95.79	98.11	98.18	98.26

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The hyperspectral model was trained with different quantizations of both activations and weights. The quantizations considered for (*activations* \times *weights*) were 8×8 , 4×4 , 2×2 , and 1×1 .

Two well-known hyperspectral data sets were considered in this work: Indian Pines (IP) and University of Pavia (UP).

The IP data set was gathered in 1992 by the Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) sensor [23] over an agricultural area in Northwestern Indiana. It covers a set of agricultural fields with regular geometry and irregular forest areas. The selected hyperspectral image has 145×145 pixels and 224 spectral bands, but only 200 bands were considered for the experiments. About half of the hyperspectral data contains ground-truth information with a single label from 16 different classes.

The UP image was acquired by the Reflective Optics System Imaging Spectrometer sensor [24] over the campus at the UP, Northern Italy. This dataset contains an urban environment with multiple structures, natural objects and shadows. After discarding noisy bands, the scene contains 103 spectral bands, with a size of 610×340 pixels. Only 20% of the pixels contain ground-truth information from nine different class labels.

A. Accuracy of the Quantized Hyperspectral Model

The model was described in PyTorch¹, an open source machine learning framework implemented in Python optimized for both CPUs and GPUs. The dataset was ported to the already developed model and the network training was done. Its worth pointing out in this model the backbone was already trained on the ImageNet dataset which decreased the overall time of the training process.

Quantization was done with Brevitas², a PyTorch library used for quantization-aware training that implements a set of building blocks at different levels of abstraction to model a reduced precision hardware data-path at training time. This library provides several quantized versions of the standard PyTorch layers that can be replaced with the original PyTorch model.

Several model configurations with different quantizations and different image path sizes were trained. For each configuration, the accuracy was determined (see Tables II and III for the IP and UP datasets, respectively).

As can be seen from the results, as the quantization reduces the number of bits to represent the weights and the activations,

TABLE III. ACCURACY OF THE HYPERSPECTRAL MODEL WITH DIFFERENT QUANTIZATIONS AND DIFFERENT PATCH SIZES FOR THE UP DATASET

Dataset: UP			
	Patch size (D)		
	7	9	11
8×8	99.85	99.93	99.96
4×4	98.84	99.56	99.97
2×2	96.13	97.22	97.73
1×1	91.24	95.62	97.28

TABLE IV. OCCUPATION OF FPGA RESOURCES OF A DOT-PRODUCT UNIT WITH 16 PARALLEL MULTIPLIERS FOR DIFFERENT QUANTIZATIONS.

	LUTs
8×8	827
4×4	291
2×2	104
1×1	48

the accuracy drops. The reduction is higher for lower patches. In fact, the smaller variation in accuracy that happens for larger patches means that there is a larger redundancy in the model that tolerates a more aggressive quantization.

To compensate the reduction in accuracy, a consequence of a more aggressive quantization, a larger patch can be used. As can be seen from the previous tables, there are some configurations with the same accuracy. For example, in the IP dataset case, the configuration with quantization 4×4 and patch = 7 has the same accuracy as the configuration with quantization 2×2 and patch = 19. Which one to choose depends on the execution time of each configuration. This aspect is analyzed in the next subsection.

B. Performance Estimation of the Quantized Hyperspectral Model

As shown in the previous section, there are different configurations of the hyperspectral model with close accuracy. The best configuration should be chosen based on the image processing throughput achieved. To avoid the hardware implementation of all configurations for comparison purposes, we consider an approach to determine the relative performance estimation of the hyperspectral model configuration.

The approach is based on the convolutional neural network accelerator proposed in [25]. The core element of the architecture is a parallel dot-product unit that is replicated multiple times to allow massive parallelism of the model. The lower the quantization, the more core elements can be used in parallel, assuming the same total hardware resources. To determine an approximation to the relative performance, we synthesized the core dot-product units for different quantizations. This allows us to establish a relative resource occupation of the target architecture for different quantizations. Given the number of operations of each configuration of the model and the relative resource occupation, we estimated the relative performance between all configurations.

The areas of the dot-product units for different configurations are given in table IV, considering a Zynq UltraScale+ XCZU7EV GPGA. These implementations assume that the dot-product unit has 16 parallel multipliers.

The number of operations of the hyperspectral model is given in V. As expected, the number of operations increases

¹<https://pytorch.org/>

²<https://github.com/Xilinx/brevitas>

TABLE V. NUMBER OF OPERATIONS OF THE HYPERSPECTRAL MODEL FOR DIFFERENT PATCHES.

Dataset: IP	
Patch	MOPS
7	64.8
9	113.6
11	168.0
15	319.9
19	520.6
21	648.0
Dataset: UP	
Patch	MOPS
7	63.5
9	111.3
11	164.6

proportionally to the square of the patch size.

With this information, the tradeoff between accuracy and the performance was determined for all configurations of the hyperspectral model (see VI).

As expected, the highest relative performance for a particular patch is obtained with the configuration with the smallest quantization. It can also be observed that the accuracy of the configurations with 4×4 quantization is very close to that of the configurations with 8×8 quantization, with just about one third of the design cost. Also, the reduction in accuracy when a more aggressive quantization is used, is higher for a lower patch.

The (*) in table VI close to the accuracy of each configuration identifies the Pareto points of the design space. All points of table VI are represented in figure 3.

The best solutions are for quantizations 4×4 and 1×1 , except for the highest patches, where the best designs are for the less aggressive quantizations. The same conclusions were observed for the UP dataset.

Therefore, a careful design of the hyperspectral model must consider both area, performance and accuracy. In embedded devices, the best solution is not necessarily the one with the highest accuracy. Therefore, this analysis is an important step in the design of CNN models for hyperspectral image analysis in hardware.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes the exploration of the design space of an implementation of an hyperspectral model for pixel segmentation in FPGA. The process considers the number of operations of the model, the design area (hardware resources) and the accuracy. Whenever the accuracy is not the most important metric, a tradeoff exists between performance, design area and accuracy. The analysis done in this paper reveals this tradeoff for an hyperspectral pixel classification model, which can be used by the designer to choose the best architecture and model configuration.

The next step is to study the impact of the number of filters in each layer over the accuracy, resources and performance. The hyperspectral model considered in this paper considers non-power of two number of filters, which is a disadvantage when implemented in hardware since, usually, the number of parallel processing units is a power of two.

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TABLE VI. ACCURACY VERSUS PERFORMANCE FOR DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS OF THE HYPERSPECTRAL MODEL FOR THE IP DATASET

dataset: IP					
Patch	Quantization	MOPS	Relative Area	Relative Performance	Accuracy
7	8 × 8	64.8	1	1.0	98.74
7	4 × 4	64.8	0.35	2.9	98.55*
7	2 × 2	64.8	0.13	7.7	91.72
7	1 × 1	64.8	0.06	16.7	84.79*
9	8 × 8	113.6	1	0.6	99.41
9	4 × 4	113.6	0.35	1.6	99.10*
9	2 × 2	113.6	0.13	4.3	94.67
9	1 × 1	113.6	0.06	9.4	93.98*
11	8 × 8	168.0	1	0.4	99.53
11	4 × 4	168.0	0.35	1.1	99.33*
11	2 × 2	168.0	0.13	3.0	96.15
11	1 × 1	168.0	0.06	6.4	95.79*
15	8 × 8	319.9	1	0.2	99.59
15	4 × 4	319.9	0.35	0.6	99.52*
15	2 × 2	319.9	0.13	1.5	98.31
15	1 × 1	319.9	0.06	3.3	98.11*
19	8 × 8	520.6	1	0.1	99.64*
19	4 × 4	520.6	0.35	0.4	99.57
19	2 × 2	520.6	0.13	0.9	98.54
19	1 × 1	520.6	0.06	2.1	98.18
21	8 × 8	648.0	1	0.1	99.73*
21	4 × 4	648.0	0.35	0.3	99.61*
21	2 × 2	648.0	0.13	0.8	98.66
21	1 × 1	648.0	0.06	1.6	98.26

Fig. 3. Design space of the quantized hyperspectral model

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